

Qualitative Study on Interdependence Learning Strategies for Effective Teaching of Social Studies at Basic Levels of Education in Nigeria

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Abstract

The paper titled qualitative study on interdependence learning strategies for effective teaching of Social Studies at basic levels of education in Nigeria. It's a descriptive review on the interdependence learning strategies as it related to Social Studies at basic levels of education in Nigeria. Effective teaching of Social Studies education at basic levels of education in Nigeria is geared towards production of active and rational citizens capable of thinking critically, analyze issues clearly, identify the problems objectively, pry into its causes, assess its effects and evolve possible means of solving them using inquiry and problem-solving approaches. This paper therefore, examined the interdependence learning strategies, Social Studies education at basic level of Nigeria education, constructivism theory position on the positive interdependence learning strategies in teaching Social Studies education at basic levels of education in Nigeria. Conclusion and recommendations were made.

Keyword: Social Studies, Interdependence, Learning strategies, Basic level of education

Introduction

Education is the bed rock for national development and basic education levels in Nigeria concept can be said to be the provision of education from the primary up to and including the first three years of the secondary level of education. Basic education is the base-line education on which all other educational advancement depend. This determines the stability of the entire educational building that anyone can ever have. Thus, it's to a large extent what determines the success or failure of all other stages of education that may come on it (Amaddioha & Akor, 2020). This means that education should be available to citizens who are willing to participate or benefit from the primary level which normally begins at the age of 6 for majority of Nigerians.

The Primary and the Junior Secondary levels of education are said to be Nigeria government's promise to provide to its citizens free but compulsory. With this idea in mind, the government made attempts to make basic education free by starting the Universal Basic Education scheme to cater for the basic educational needs of its citizens to justify catch them young approach where pupils are well prepared for their better future. This will also help to make the learners' law abiding, critical thinkers and problem solvers of their beloved country Nigeria. Social Studies as a subject was a product of 1969 curriculum conference that brought about Nigeria education blue print called national policy on Education of different editions. This conference was called on the need to rebuild Nigeria from the bondage of foreign administrators that was not only exploitive but also dehumanizing. Among the remarkable landmarks of the conference was the formulation of national philosophy and national educational objectives. It is worthy to note that, the educational objectives was developed to facilitate realization of national philosophy through which Social Studies objectives were derived. However, Nigeria philosophy as a nation is to achieve a free and democratic society; a just and egalitarian society; a united, strong and self-reliant nation; a great and dynamic economy; and a land of bright and full opportunities for all citizens (Federal Republic of Nigeria {FRN}, 2013).

In line with above, national educational aims and objectives in Nigeria are the inculcation of national consciousness and national unity; the inculcation of the right type of values and attitudes for survival of the individual and the Nigeria society; the training of mind to understanding the world around; and the acquisition of appropriate skills, abilities and competencies both mental and physical and equipping the individual to live in and contribute to the development of his country (FRN, 2013). The objectives of Social Studies education at Nigeria basic education levels are to: create an awareness and an understanding of the evolving social and physical environment as a whole, its natural, man-made, cultural and spiritual resources, together with the national use and conservation of these resources for development; develop a capacity to learn and acquire certain skills which are essential to the formation of satisfactory professional life and the forming of sound judgment; ensure the acquisition of knowledge that is relevant and regarded as an essential pre-requisite to personal development as well as to a positive personal contribution to the betterment of mankind; develop in children positive attitudes to citizenship and a desire in them to make a

positive personal contribution to the creation of a united Nigeria; develop a sympathetic appreciation of the diversity and interdependence of all members of the local community and the wider national and international communities so that they would become aware of the problem of their country and the world in general; and develop in children an appreciation of the nation's cultural heritage and desire to preserve such heritage (Owen, 2022).

Also, students' interdependence in teaching and learning process cannot be overemphasized. Hence, in order to make instructional delivery effective, there is need for paradigm shift in the instructional process using variant learning strategies include positive interdependence learning strategies (Usman, 2024). There are two types of interdependence learning approaches namely positive and negative interdependence. Positive interdependence are cooperative and collaborative while competitive learning strategy formed negative interdependence (Johnson & Johnson, 2018). However, when the needed result is not arrived at from neither process, the teacher resort to individualized approach. The purpose of this article is targeted on the quantitative study on interdependence learning strategies for effective teaching of social studies at Basic levels of Education in Nigeria. Constructivism theory of positive interdependence learning strategies namely collaborative and cooperative learning strategies as well as the relevance of interdependence learning strategies in social studies education were reviewed.

Conceptual Reviews of Social Studies Education and Interdependence Learning Strategies for Effective Teaching of Social Studies at Basic levels of education in Nigeria

Social Studies Education at Basic levels of education in Nigeria

Nigeria education has different levels with levels designed for categories of its beneficiaries. On the definition of social studies, experts of social studies concluded that, there is no single universal acceptable definition of social studies. However, the concept of social studies can be understood within the context of the objectives which underline the philosophy and aims of the society's education (Ikumelu *et al.*, & Oyibe, 2015). This is true of all countries which have Social Studies in their school curricula. This is clearly stated in all the editions of Nigeria national policy on education. National Council for the Social Studies United States in Eduviere (2018) defines Social Studies as "an integrated study of the social sciences and humanities to promote civic competence". This definition revealed relevance of social studies education and that is civic competence. Abubakar (2013) defined social studies education as a field of study that instils in students the knowledge, skills, attitudes and actions that are considered important in the relationship and interaction of man and those around him on one hand, and the entire environment on the other hands.

Social Studies Education can be used in Nigeria to achieve peace, minimize ethnic problems in various states, tribalism, sectionalism, bribery and corruption, hatred, anger, rigging of elections, cultism in institutions of learning, students unrest, prostitution, examination malpractice, armed robbery, kidnappings, assassinations, forgery, suicide bombing, religious conflicts, and many other social vices in our society. Social studies is a unique subject that is committed towards transmitting values in citizens and assist them to acquire basic designed body of knowledge, skills and attitudes needed for responsible citizenship for Nigeria development (Opoh & Edinyang, 2014).

Theoretical Perspectives on Interdependence Learning Strategy: Constructivism Theory

Learning theory can be viewed as an approach that describe how subject matter, learning content or skills are acquired, absorbed, processed and retained for future context. It provides explanations of the factors that influence learning and instructional guidelines to overcome them. Constructivism Learning Theory according to Padgett (2020), sees learners as a constructor of knowledge. As propounded by Lev Vygotsky (1978), constructivism learning theory hold that, learning is a collaborative process, and that social interaction is rudimental to cognitive development of the learners. It stated that, learners learn best when working collaboratively with those whose proficiency level is higher than their own, allowing them to complete tasks they are not yet able to do independently (Padgett, 2020).

Makewa (2019) also stated that constructivism theory hold that learning take place if learner construct mechanisms for it using his/her own unique talents and argued that, academic knowledge need to be constructed by the learners with teacher as guidance and motivator by creating conducive learning environment. It further stated that, the learners' engagement actively is key to achieve the instructional set goals. McLeod (2019) stated that, constructivism theory requires that academic knowledge and authority should be shared between students and their teachers, serve as facilitators of learning. Hence, learning group should consist small heterogeneous number of students. The learning implications of this theory is that, there should be adequate teachers' guide to help the learners to apply their knowledge to solve learning problems. Learners centred learning approaches are emphasized because they allow the learners' self-control and decision-making based on knowledge and ideas (Hartmann, *et al.*, 2017). Positive interdependence are cooperative and collaborative and these discussed as follows.

Collaborative Learning Strategies at Basic level of education in Nigeria

Collaborative learning strategy as the name implies, involves grouping of learners of the basic educational level to work together as an instructional team to achieve set instructional objectives. Collaborative learning can be defined as an instructional approach where students work together in small group on specific activities where everyone is required to participate actively. Adolphus *et al.* (2013) viewed it as pedagogical system which learners engage in a common task where each individual depends on and is accountable to each other. This strategy placed learners at basic education levels to be actively involved in the learning processes in which they assimilate information and relate the new knowledge to their cognitive structure for future utilization and subsequent learning tasks. It is an instructional approach in which students work together in small groups to solve learning problem, accomplish a common instructional goals or create a product (Jibrin *et al.*, 2021).

Collaborative learning strategy is one of the positive interdependence in the learning process based on the assumption that academic knowledge and skills can be created within a population where members actively interact by sharing experiences and take on asymmetry roles. It allow learners at basic education levels in the group to share academic ability and contribute their personal knowledge through sharing of responsibilities among the members and accept fruitful views from the members (Chandra, 2015). The author further stated that, collaborative learning activities operate on the principles that, learners at the basic levels of education are the primary focus of instruction, interaction and doing as well as working in group.

Akinwamide (2018) stated that, increase students' tolerance and acceptance of diversity; communication and social skills; and enhancement of students' academic interests as well their academic performance formed critical features of collaborative learning strategy. Abubakar and Arshad (2015) maintained that, collaborative learning entails students debating their ideas and viewpoints on the learning issues through presentations and interactions in groups. It gives them ability to appreciate a variety of other viewpoints to successfully carry out the assigned task with people from diverse backgrounds. This learning strategy engage students actively in the learning process and places more responsibility of comprehension on them; their role is shifted to a more active approach rather than being lectured and getting information passively. Evaluate speaking ability of students in real-life situations because it plays a pivotal role in everyday life interactions.

Agah (2020) stated that, collaborative learning helps to eliminate misconceptions and lack of understanding thus, better understanding and higher achievement are enhanced. It also enable the teacher, the learners and educators share a common aspiration of ensuring that appropriate skills are inculcated in and acquired by the learner. Collaborative learning encourages critical thinking skills to students much better than individualistic learning environments (Jibrin, *et al.*, 2021).

Cooperative Learning Strategies at Basic level of education in Nigeria

Cooperative learning strategy is another innovated teaching method in which students of different ability work together in groups to accomplish the assigned instructional goals. Hence, the students work together as a team with the aim of achieving the purpose for which they agreed to come together to promote their learning as well as their teammates learning (Bukar *et al.*, 2020). Ihejiamazu *et al.*, (2020) and Philemon and Nonye (2019) defined cooperative learning strategy as a method used for small groups in which pupils/students' work together to gain from each other. In cooperative learning, students work together to maximize and gain from each other. The students/pupils are expected to help, discuss and argue their points with each other, assess each other's current knowledge, and fill any gaps. Here, the students of cooperative group do not assume mastery of the effort which leads to the success of the group as each member actively contributes to the success of the group.

David (2019) describe cooperative learning strategy as the learning strategy where students' are assigned to small groups in the classroom as well as another environment in which they help each other to learn together, cooperate to have positive achievement to attain academic goals, increase the self-confidence of individual students, develop good communication skills and fully participate actively in the learning process. The strategy involves assigning students to a learning objective; the teacher who assigns that instructional objectives serves as guardian and supervisor to ensure that students attain the specific objective that was set to achieve.

The reasons for cooperative learning are to promote students' learning and academic achievement; enhance students' satisfaction with their learning experience; help students develop skills in oral communication; develop social skills & promote student self-esteem; help to promote positive relations that can lead to gain high students academic achievement (Bukar *et al.*, 2020). Philemon and Nonye (2019) also stated that, the aim of cooperative method of teaching is to bring students together in a relatively small group to pursue a specific task as well as promoting teamwork among the students. Bukar *et al.* (2020) identified five elements of cooperative learning strategy to include positive interdependence; individual accountability; face-to face interaction; appropriate use of collaborative skills; and group processing. To do these, they recommended five steps to be used by teachers during cooperative learning setting. These are introduction; divide the students into group of five; assign activities to be carried by each group; discussion on the concept taught and evaluation.

In a cooperative learning classroom students' structure, students discuss the instructional content, assist the peers to learn, and provide encouragement for members of the group to learn. The strategy promote more positive attitudes towards the instructional experiences than competitive or individualistic methodologies (David, 2019). He affirmed that students benefit academically and socially from cooperative learning.

Difference between Collaborative and Cooperative Learning Strategies at Basic level of education in Nigeria

Although, cooperative and collaborative learning strategies are used interchangeably, the two strategies are not the same. Bhopal (2023) and Chandra (2020) itemized the followings as the basic differences between collaborative and cooperative learning strategies.

1. Collaborative learning strategy involves division of students into several independent instructional groups while cooperative involves division of learners at basic education levels into small instructional groups under the guidance of their teacher. This implies that, cooperative is more of teacher centred than collaborative.
2. Collaborative strategy involve collective problem solving while cooperative involves clear role assignment by the teacher.
3. Collaborative involves group participation in the assigned task while cooperative requires task division for individual efforts.
4. In collaborative learning strategy, learners at basic education levels to dominate learning process while in cooperative, teachers' structured learning process for the students.
5. In collaborative learning strategy, mutual cooperation, involvement, and combined efforts of the learners at basic education levels are involved while in cooperative various aspects of the instructional tasks are determined, and learners at basic education levels are given the responsibility of finding a solution to different aspects which is then integrated to solve the problem.
6. In collaborative strategy, learners in the instructional team works together sequentially on different aspect of task assigned to them while in cooperative learning strategy, students works concurrently on different aspects of the given task.

Review of related studies on Interdependence learning strategies.

Usman (2024), Niyonsaba *et al*, (2022). Wokocha and Allen (2021), Agah (2020), Anthony *et al* (2018), and Okwelle and Owo (2018) in their various studies found that, students taught using collaborative learning strategy outperformed their counter parts taught with other conventional methods of teaching. This implies that, improvement in students' academic performance as observed from the students taught with collaborative learning strategy. Similarly, students taught using collaborative learning strategy recorded higher problem solving abilities and learning motivation than those taught with the conventional method (Adolphus *et al*, 2013). This also underscore the problem solving as an integral part of social studies objectives. Furthermore, empirical researches on cooperative learning strategy revealed that, group of students taught with cooperative learning strategy performed better than those taught with other teaching methods like lecture, discussion and etc. This finding further necessitate the need to adopt and apply cooperative learning strategy (Usman, 2024, Ihejiamaizu, *et al*, 2020, Ibemenji *et al*, 2019, Gabriel *et al*, 2018, and Stephen, 2017). Also, students taught using cooperative learning strategy also retained significantly better in than those taught with conventional method (Usman, 2024, Akinlande & Jacob, 2020).

Conclusion

This article looked into qualitative study on interdependence learning strategies for effective teaching of social studies at basic levels of education in Nigeria. Based on the discussion and deliberation of this article, it is believed that, positive interdependence learning strategies for effective teaching of social studies at basic levels of education in Nigeria will promote interdependence among social studies pupils at basic level of Nigeria education; promote we-feeling and unity of purpose; inculcate dialogue skills during deliberation towards problem solving; promote group discussion skills to generate ideas and solve problem; foster teamwork and cooperation; help the students to develop problem-solving skills; facilitate human diversity in the group relationship; and stimulate active participation in the group activities.

Positive interdependence learning strategies mainly cooperative and collaborative has enormous instructional impacts. Thus, there is need to equip Social Studies teachers on the use of it through training and re-training, close monitoring and supportive supervision to pave way for on the job training as well as to increase Social Studies teachers teaching morale. This will go a long ways to facilitate students' interactive and participatory learning thereby making learning a light in their mind instead of burden in their memory.

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